

Thinking urban informality through southern theory

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Abstract:

This article investigates urban informality via the lens of southern theory and sets out a postcolonial conceptual framework for researching and theorizing the urban. The article develops the framework via arguing towards advancing ontological queries rather than epistemological probing. To this end, it proposes to investigate the urban via informality and not the other way around, of understanding informality as an anomaly to, the constructed notions of the urban.

Key words:

Urban informality, southern theory, knowledge hegemony, urban geography, urban poor.

I Introduction

A fast urbanizing world has been urban geography's major concern since the turn of the century, reiterated by the ubiquitous phrase that more than half of humans now live in cities (owing to United Nations Centre for Human Settlements, 2001). Global South's gigantic contribution to this process is another sub-concern, as the majority of these urban dwellers are living in the so-called, substandard 'informal settlements' and slums (Amin, 2013; Gleeson, 2012). Consequently, attention is turning to shift urban theory's locus to the global South for countering the universal narratives based out of a few influential Northern cities (Comaroff and Comaroff, 2012; Connell, 2011; Lawhon and Le Roux, 2019; Robinson, 2016; Roy, 2011; Watson, 2009). The claim being, if the majority of urbanization is happening in the global South, then we need to understand this, using theories from the South and not by imposing the ones developed using the Northern cities as a model – making urban theory global (Edensor and Jayne, 2012; Ghertner, 2015b; Lawhon and Truelove, 2020; Lemanski, 2014). Southern theory divulges the process that facilitates the concentration of power and knowledge in the metropolis (North/West at a global scale) and marginalizes learning from the periphery – investigating and countering the geography of knowledge hegemony (Houssay-Holzschuch, 2020; Palat Narayanan, 2020a, 2020b). Informality, on the other hand, has been initially conceptualized in the 1970s with the ILO country mission report on Kenya (ILO and UNDP, 1972) and writing of Keith Hart (1973), which discussed the informal economy. Ever since, the discourse on the informal has been shifting, with major conceptualizations still arising out of the studies from the global south. From informality as a parasite in the 1980s, to de Soto's (2002) claim of looking at informality as a solution by capitalizing on the frugal entrepreneurialism of the urban poor, to the apocalyptic picturization by Davis (2007), and finally urban informality as a dominant normality and as a type of negotiation and valuation in postcolonial worlding cities by Roy and AlSayyad (2004), all have been using various means to understand and (re)conceptualize informality. The subject of study, i.e., informality, is set in an urban debate and as distinct from formality, has led to become what McFarlane (2012: 89) postulates, "...one of the most enduring in urban and planning theory..."

What then is informality? This question has been at the core of the discussions which developed multifarious boundaries and understandings of this concept (Acuto et al., 2019; Boanada-Fuchs and Fuchs, 2018; Bunnell and Harris, 2012; Davis, 2017; McFarlane and Waibel, 2016). I will augment responses to this question, from a two

interrelated theoretical manoeuvres. First, the Habermas-ian (1971) notion of human interest¹ in knowledge production. This will help us in reading the literature thus forth on urban informality with regard to the interest for which informality is conceptualized therein. That is, if knowledge is inherently a result of human interest, then it puts knowledge production under the realm of (human) politics, a quintessential southern theory axiom. Second, is to investigate the knowledge relationships which result in the seemingly contradictory dualism of formal-informal. The article therefore, investigates the variegated notions of urban informality from the vantage point of its theoretical conception and thereafter, enquire the larger urban knowledge production nexus that led to this conception, using southern theory (however within the limited frame of human geography). I argue that, by turning the question of, how informality operates/generates/valuates in the urban, into, understanding the urban *via* informality, we can take the positionality of the researcher out of the metropolitan biases and as a result, broaden both the southern theory discussions as well as the urban informality ones. I will develop how and why the study of urban informality has been the domain of epistemological innovation and why a focus on ontological query is now quintessential for the southern turn, or to read the periphery without situating it with respect to the metropolis.

In the following three sections, I will chronologically build the larger argument of how various interest has been mobilized to conceptualize informality. This perpetual cycle of conceptualizing informality can only be understood by moving out of the formal-informal dualism and investigating it within the urban knowledge production nexus albeit not relegating the theoretical potential of the term informal. The key feature of informality is its adaptability and how various domains have moulded it using different suffixes and meanings. Therefore, it becomes easier to investigate these conceptions in a rough chronological order; however, the attempt is not to illustrate a linear deterministic historical progression. In the following section (II), I will discuss the initial conceptions of informality as a sector. This economic reading has set the basis for future

¹ Habermas (1971) argues that theory's role is to bring out the human interests that moulded the knowledge production. He calls for a critique countering objectivism's false impression in scientific knowledge, suggesting: "... objectivism is eliminated not through the power of renewed *theoria* [by detachments to any practical interest and moving to classical philosophical tradition] but through demonstrating what it conceals: the connection of knowledge and [human] interest". (Habermas, 1971: 316 – 17)

(re)conceptualizations of informality, as an anomaly to the urban, which necessitates a shift towards an informal-urban dialectic away from formal-informal dichotomy. This fundamental understanding of informal-urban dialectic is thereafter taken forward to the contemporary context in section III. Section III outlines the process which makes marginalization as a major focus of informality studies and proposes its modification for a southern turn. Finally, section IV outlines the operationalization of informal-urban dialectic and how a southern theory reading leads to a renewed study of informality, as a critique of urban.

II Reduction: Initial conceptions and Informal-urban dialectic

In the 1970s, the ILO report (ILO and UNDP, 1972) and Hart's (1973) work theorized informality from an economic angle and brought it to international limelight using the term informal sector. The interest here was to capture the totality of the economy (within the political boundaries of a country), which could not be grasped by mere analysis of registered economic activities. This meant looking at economic activities outside the domain of the state's register. The notion of informality in the informal sector is not just of the mere unregistered petty businesses, but that of the social condition of precarity, plurality of activities, and forced bracketing, i.e., labour being the main focus. In that, the people engaged in the informal sector are precariously employed (without the usual social security measures), they have multiple but insufficient modes of earnings, and these are not choices, but result of an unfair economic system. Hart (1973) delineated the informal sector as consisting of people who could not make enough money through the formal system and therefore, required to seek alternative means. This conceptual splitting of economy into two abstract forms of formal and informal, produced a further comprehensive understanding of economy, but a geographical reading demonstrated a concrete cluster-formation of such economic activities (Harriss-White, 2009, 2017). Informality as a sector is an abstract concept, however, economic clustering of this sector and embodiment of these practices by marginalized citizens, linked informality to people and places. This linking is important in understanding the future (re)conceptualization of informality and its possible adaptation to the southern turn in human geography.

The economic delineation of formal-informal sector did not demand its association with people and places (or even a negative picturization). Hart (1973), aiming to improve the condition of labour in Accra, led to a study that took into account a large group of

migrants, their employment status, education levels, skills, and economic conditions. He was acutely aware of a negative rendering as he writes (while describing 'illegitimate activities' in a neighbourhood where informal-sector labour formed a cluster):

The system of bourgeois values enshrined in a nation's code of laws may not coincide with concepts of legitimacy prevalent in certain subcultures of that society. (Hart, 1973: 74)

Although Hart managed to point out the split between what is prevalent and what becomes legal in economy, these notions were not carried forward to the spatiality of economic clustering (a concern that resurfaced later in geography discussions of the 21st century). Hart's work had two major consequences. First, pointing to the lower education levels, migration status, and poverty, made these deficiencies as tropes through which informality got associated, i.e., informality as a southern city characteristic resulting in or resultant of, poverty and underdevelopment. Second, his stress on insufficiency of the Western economic model and illustration of social complexities in African cities led to a romantic notion of the frugal entrepreneurship and the endurance of the urban poor. This frame of reference was thereafter picked up in other countries (cf. Sen, 1976).

The binary of formal-informal sector was subsequently reformulated, from Breman's (1976) pointing of its analytical inadequacy, to Santos's (1979) notion of circuits, which analysed informal economy beyond national boundaries, and Portes and Schauffler's (1993) showcasing that informal sector is neither homogeneous nor independent of the formal sector, bringing the epistemological question on, how to better understand this sector, to the forefront. The economic enquiry frame of informality continues (Daniels, 2004; Gerry, 1987; Harriss-White, 2017; Papola, 1980), which, however, is not of interest for this article. The embodiment of informality onto specific people and places sustained throughout the 1970s and 1980s, especially in geography and allied disciplines reading human habitats (cf. Turner (1977)). Thus, there are two main interrelated factors arising here, which is of interest for this article. First, the ontological placement of informal within the larger conception of the urban. The urban here remains unquestioned, but the investigations are turned onto the working of informal (as a spatial and bodily category). Second, is the notion of this unquestioned urban itself, as to where its formulations lie. This circumscription of informality – of conceptually placing

informality within urban and not questioning the conception of urban when investigating informality – is the focus of critique in the article.

This theoretical outline has had very concrete implications in the policy domain. In the 64 recommendations made by The Vancouver Declaration on Human Settlements (Habitat-I) (1976), there emerged a section (recommendation C.8) dedicated to the informal sector's role in housing provision. Habitat-I largely concentrated on the settlement and the related human conditions. It used the term informal sector, although broadening its understanding from the economy to housing and infrastructure provision as well. Habitat-I delineated the informal sector as a process by the 'less advantaged' to provide means of living for themselves. It therefore suggested that the states stabilize land tenure and to provide technical and financial assistance, as well as infrastructure for basic amenities, specifically in the form of 'sites and services' scheme (adapted and popularized later by de Soto (2001, 2002) as a transformation of housing from use-value to exchange-value, which was later critiqued (Nijman, 2008; Varley, 2002)).

The attention towards slums became the counterpart of economy-led discussions of the informal sector, making slums a geographically delineated political subject, which needed to be understood (an epistemological manoeuvre). Studying slums, Marris famously wrote:

“A slum is only a slum in the eyes of someone for whom it is an anomaly – a disruption of the urban form and relationships which to that observer seem appropriate to his or her own values and perception.”(Marris, 1979: 419)

Critiquing various housing projects, Marris puts slums as a settlement type in itself, which was wrongly seen in a negative light, bringing about an epistemological rupture. He, however, did not deny the issues and problems within slums, but set out to highlight the complexity of this urban form. Here too, the slums are circumscribed in an urban (conceptualization of urban), which is unquestioned, and anomalies to which becomes the definition of a slum (de Antuñano, 2020). Perlman (1979) approached this problematic of Marris by disassociating slums/*favela* (housing) from marginality, she argued:

“The key point here is that marginality is not caused by poor housing conditions or by characteristics of individuals or groups, but by forms of society rooted in the

historical process of industrialization and economic growth in the developing nations...” (Perlman, 1979: 251)

Perlman’s work rendered slums as a symptom of larger economic disparities, therefore, actions on slums could not be equated to socio-economic development. Her work problematized the slums and the larger economic structure into an interrelated mesh. However, in the policy domain, the indication of slums as poor housing condition and its eradication as development, continued (*United Nations Conference on Human Settlements (Habitat-II)*, 1996) which got heavily critiqued later (Arabindoo, 2011; Gilbert, 2007; Huchzermeyer, 2014).

The urban in all the cases remain a vessel which hosts various formations of informality. If informality is a glitch in the urban, then what defines this urban or what defines the non-informal, i.e., formal? The notion of informality has in itself embedded the notion of the urban. If informality is an anomaly to the urban, then this anomaly contains in itself the notions of the urban, which it is an anomaly of. Thus, informality has to be understood by exercising a dialectic between the informal and urban, where formal is subsumed within the understanding of the urban. It breaks the reading of formal-informal dualism as operating within the urban, thus bringing the urban conceptualization and southern theory to the heart of informality discussions and away from the teleological investigations of both informal and urban.

Formal exists only to be able to define informal. No one ever studied, say water supply system of a formal settlement, it merely will be a study of urban water supply. A formal settlement is a notion whose existence purely depends on the usage of the term ‘informal-settlement’. This othering of informal has been discussed before (Acuto et al., 2019; Boudreau and Davis, 2017) however, it juggles the nefarious duality of formal-informal. This theoretical knot of formal-informal can never be untied because the existence of one is theoretically impossible without the other. Further, this binary is situated (as it) independently in the urban, which acts as a context. To look beyond the formal-informal dichotomy is to admit that formal and urban are the same. It is the urban that is rephrased as formal to be able to legitimize the theoretical existence of informal and the dependence on this concept. However, positing informal and urban, in a dialectic relationship opens theoretical possibilities of questioning both the informal and urban, making informality embedded in the urban (and an urban which is beyond

being merely formal). I will further develop this informal-urban dialectic in the following sections.

Additionally, it becomes pertinent here to de-link informality from its euphemisms – from socio-economic marginalization to inadequate civic services – as well as modifications by suffixes like settlement, housing, institutions, infrastructure, etc. This also points to the ontological question of ‘what then is the need for the concept of informality’, rather than the epistemological one of, ‘what is informality’. If informality is merely a substitute for rather well-defined notions of legal-illegal, oppression, marginalization, etc. then its use is altogether superficial, riding the popularity wave of an irrelevant protagonist. If informality, on the other hand, is a conducive concept, then it definitely cannot be used in place of concepts listed above or any combinations thereof.

Thus, the discussion of initial informality conceptions leads us to two notions. First, informality has to be understood within a dialectic of informal-urban, rather than the binary of formal-informal. Second, informality need not be used as a substitute for other well-established concepts, making terms like ‘informal-settlements’ theoretically redundant. I will carry forward the first notion, which also raises the problematic of how then to investigate informality. It is to be noted here that in the initial economic conception of informal sector, it was the economic choices and financial practices that formed the object of enquiry, although discussed using its embodiment in people and places. Discussion of informality as a practice (Cirolia and Scheba, 2019; Dovey, 2010; McFarlane, 2012; Palat Narayanan, 2019) brings out the mobilization of this concept beyond it being a substitute for other concepts (as discussed above) and as a base for exploring it within the informal-urban dialectic. To read informality as a practice is to primarily move out of its association with people and places. It is to render only the practice as informal, which can be practised by an array of people in an array of places. It does take the body of the practitioners into account so does the places, but is not associated with it. The association of informality to people and places restricts the investigations merely to what Lefebvre (1991) called ‘representation of space’, as Simone lucidly argued:

“Particular spaces are linked to specific identities, functions, lifestyles, and properties so that the spaces of city become legible for specific people at given places and time.”(Simone, 2004: 409)

In this section, we have narrowed the informality concern to two main motives. First, to de-link informality from other concepts such as poverty, marginality, illegality, domination, etc. It therefore, requires to read informality as a practice. Second, taking the formal-informal dichotomy towards informal-urban dialectic. Using these two arguments, in the next section, I will build how urban is an inbuilt negation in the conception of informal, thereby the need to understand the urban using informal (and not to understand informal using urban, where informal becomes an anomaly to the urban).

III Deconstruction: Informality in the age of urban

Before moving on to further conceptualizations of informality, let us revisit the informal-urban dialectic. Urban informality can either be an anomaly to the urban (as an unwanted other, a glitch, a problem to be solved) or part of it (as a constituent). We have seen in the previous section that if informality is conceptualized as an anomaly to the urban, then it raises the question of what defines this urban. This is in light of the various southern theory investigations, which highlights how the ‘southern tropes’ (Schindler, 2017) arises from the fact that our current theoretical models based out of northern experiences could not capture the urban realities elsewhere (Ghertner, 2015b; Lemanski, 2014). Therefore, the anomaly model, is itself a result of, or proof of, our theoretical inadequacies. We need informality, only to still be able to apply our metropolitan theories to the vast majority of the periphery. The initial conception of informal sector was thus needed for the notion of economy – as consisting of ‘formal’ sector – to be implementable in the periphery (informal sector as an outside of formal sector). The discussion of informality as an anomaly cannot lead us any further than to merely demanding the improvement of our theoretical tools. The second notion of informality as a constituent part of the urban may help in this regard. If informality is part of the urban, then studying informality (like the investigations of infrastructures, economies, culture, architecture, etc.) will help us in understanding and broadening the notions of urban. This leads to two further remounts, first, that it questions the established notions of the urban. That is, if informality is a constituent of urban, then its study will help us better understand and reformulate our current notions of the urban. Second, it requires delimiting the notion of informality, heuristically to an extent, that it can be investigated – which I briefly discussed in the previous section as

practice (informality as a practice delinked from people and places yet operated by people in places).

The first question to answer when reading informality as a constituent of urban, is – why then is informality been largely a study of the urban poor? Although one can trace the focus on poverty (and urban poor) to the initial informal-sector studies, there is a factor of interest, on power and space in geography, which has contributed to this, that becomes clearer by juxtaposing two important works. First, Roy's (2011: 233) work, which showed how informality is not just the domain of urban poor:

Informal urbanization is as much the purview of wealthy urbanites as it is of slum dwellers. These forms of urban informality — from Delhi's farmhouses to Kolkata's new towns to Mumbai's shopping malls — are no more legal than the metonymic slum. But they are expressions of class power and can therefore command infrastructure, services and legitimacy.

Roy, as many others before and after her (Arabindoo, 2016; Baviskar, 2003; Ghertner, 2015a) has established that certain informal (practices not registered by the state) and sometimes illegal practices (practices forbidden by the registered laws of the state) operates in the urban. However, the rich and influential class, garner state legitimacy for the very same practices for which the poor are penalized. This notion can be further expanded using Bayat's (1997) work, who developed a narrative of the politics of informality within the larger context of the Islamic revolution in Iran. His study not only linked the informal practices (mainly of the urban poor) to the larger national context of revolution in Iran (beyond economics), but also presented the conflict with the State. Bayat (2007) tried to answer broader questions like that of a false link between the dispossessed urban dwellers and radical Islam. Bayat's work presents a nuanced understanding of the informal practices and the reasoning for highlighting it using the practices of the urban poor. His work can be read as contributing to the power dynamics and class conflicts of informal practices in three ways – reading informality (i) within the larger geopolitics of marginality (ii) with regard to state oppression and hegemony, and (iii) the helplessness of the urban poor with respect to both the state and global capitalism. Juxtaposing Roy and Bayat demonstrates that the interest of studying informality as limited to the practices of the urban poor, has specifically been to highlight the marginalization and class domination/hegemony. Ghertner's (2015a) showcasing the usage of aesthetics to legitimize illegality of the rich or its mobilization

for the disenfranchisement of poor (by the rich) as illustrated by Müller (2017) are examples of this. Furthermore, these studies, however, need to be read in a broader urban context which is ghastly globalizing (Bogaert, 2011; Weinstein, 2008). As the violence of urbanization (Auyero, 2000; Mahadevia and Desai, 2019; Pedrazzini et al., 2014; Rodgers, 2012) becomes the locus of enquiry, the focus on marginalization takes centre stage in the informality discussions.

The marginalization discussion gets further problematized by the changes in the global capital circulation patterns. By the late 1990s, Santos's (1979) concerns of global capital were taking a new turn with many countries around the world, opening their economy to global capital. In her influential work, Sassen (1991) explored the patterns of foreign investments and impacts of financial industry, and presented a new global economic order. This economic order or hierarchy consisted of global cities (global nodes) which controlled the major capital routes of the globe. Sassen's work presented an unprecedented effect of global capital on urbanization and the city. This, on one hand, increased the focus on global systems in urban studies, and on the other hand, presented a general paradigm of looking at interconnectedness. Further, James Scott's (1990) work around the same time on peasant societies brought in a voice from below. Scott (1998) studied how the specific development moves (or acts to understand) by the state has transformed societies and yet failed to improve human condition. In this context, not only the urbanization process, but also the city was to be seen as entangled in multiple dimensions (cf., Swyngedouw's (1996) work of linking nature and humans to an extent that they cannot be separated). In such a paradigm, the informal sector could not be studied in isolation, and thus, began the enquiry into the larger realm of urban informality and a move away from the idea of an informal-sector, leading to Roy and AlSayyad's (2004) theorization of it as a governance tool.

Roy and AlSayyad (2004) conceptualized informality as a governance tool, which the State can operationalize to marginalize a set of population and/or fuel 'development' (Baviskar, 2013). When the State marks slums as illegitimate and set out to demolish it, the marking of the slum becomes possible by mobilizing this tool (Paul, 2006; Rao, 2013). Further, because of this marginalization, when the marginalized act/resist, then informality emanates as a negotiation of value:

“If formality operates through the fixing of value, including the mapping of spatial value, then informality operates through the constant negotiability of value and unmapping of spaces.”(Roy and AlSayyad, 2004: 5)

The focus on marginalization led to read informality as an opposition to the urban (or the constructed notion of urban as formal) and has added state in the analysis of it (Boudreau, 2019; Boudreau and Davis, 2017; Haid and Hilbrandt, 2019; Hilbrandt, 2019). Developing these ideas further in one of her later works (to be read from an urban planning perspective), Roy (2005, 2009) argued that planning in the global south is not about forecasting and management of growth, but about management of resources through the process of informality. This management includes various processes, including that of the un-mapping, where land is unmapped (e.g., from agriculture/rural to urban) in a process to realize certain politically driven development goals. Developing the notion of informality, she augmented that (i) informality is not synonymous with poverty (ii) informality is a state of deregulation and not an unregulated space, and (iii) the state in itself is enmeshed in informality. These epistemological and methodological investigations came together to what Roy (2011) called subaltern urbanism. She drew on the difference between global cities (which are the nodes of global capital and thus developed) and the megacities (which are the fast-growing cities of the South characterized by underdevelopment). She argued how megacities are the subalterns of urban studies, as they mark the “limits of archival and ethnographic recognition” (Roy, 2011: 224). Thus, arguing that if urban has to be understood beyond the western models, then the megacities and the processes within them need to be rendered as urban (Roy, 2016).

In the policy discussions as well, the urban took a centre stage and the 2016 Habitat-III was titled the New Urban Agenda (Habitat-III) (2016), and informality became the heart of the ‘sustainable development’ discussions. The quality of life issues, discussed in Habitat-I & II, got further linked to informality in Habitat-III. Informality in Habitat-III has been understood as poverty which is spatially contained. Such linking put the focus on spatial segregation and devising a national policy framework for spatial integration. Thus, it has put the focus on inclusive development and reiterated previously discussed (in Habitat I & II) strategies of innovative financing, participation, and planning, away from the politics of development (Harriss, 2002, 2002; Taylor and Broeders, 2015). The main thematic is that the urbanization process is excluding certain groups of people, therefore focused spatial planning (instead of larger economic

concerns) would be able to remedy this situation. A well-planned urban policy and a capable market were seen as agents that could play a crucial role in this. Thus, conceptualizing informality as a problem which can be cured by urban policies.

Such conceptualizations of the urban put the state in a dubious position. On one hand, the state was not important because it was playing along the games of global capitalism, while, on the other hand, the state became ever brutal, because it had now become the agent of the global capital which was further marginalizing the vast majority of the population (Dembowski, 2001; Heller and Partha, 2015; Kudva, 2009; Schindler, 2016). This approach found echoes at the city scale as well, e.g., in India, the state started to symbolize as working for/by the middle-class ideology and exclusionary development projects of global capital. Baviskar (2002) in her work outlined how the state policies under the influence of global capital have been marginalizing the population, and at the same time this marginalized population in the city is being further persecuted. Her work looked at what she called “bourgeois environmentalism” (Baviskar, 2003: 90) as an organized political force to highlight the displacement of the urban poor, arising from the new global image-conscious urban middle-class in India. As her work, looked at the middle-class and its influence/control over the state, the state agency of planning became central (making Roy’s work more pertinent). This brings back the classic framework of informality based on the binary theorization of the context, into the formal and the informal (or planned vs. unplanned) where the economically weaker sections of the society are seen as living in the ruptures of the legal systems and is called the informal, although the distinctions between formal-informal becoming more complex (Berner, 2000; Koster and Nuijten, 2016; Mahadevia, 2010; Raman, 2015; Schindler, 2014). The formal being the desirable urban as rendered from the metropolis and informality the anomaly, the periphery. Informality thus became an anarchic appropriation of what could not be absorbed or accommodated in the formal – although formal and informal not being mutually exclusive. Contrarily, formal became the desirable and planned, the urban, which is closest, to the Western city model, resulting in the globalization of the urban debates (Simone, 2001; Söderström, 2014).

In this section, we see how urban marginalization and resistance have been theorized using informality, in which, land (and in general, space) became the analytical category. It is understood that informal practices are not merely the domain of the marginalized, the investigations, however, resulted from studying the marginalized populations and their practices. Although relevant, these studies form the cluster around understanding

informality (an epistemological manoeuvre), and place it as complex valuation process within the urban. Consequently, the politics of informality is rendered visible by keeping the notion of urban as the base. Therefore, to question the urban, we will need to move beyond the marginalization discussions towards reading the urban via informality.

IV Construction: Informality as a mode of urban enquiry

Let us revisit the conceptualization of informality as a practice within the informal-urban dialectic. Informality, as previously discussed, can be practised by – the state and the citizenry, poor and the rich. If informality can be practised by any citizen (theoretically so) then the question that arises is – how certain conceptualizations get termed as informal? There can be two possible answers to this question. First, a positivist way of looking at informality as a practice not registered by the state, thus practices from street-vending to internet-based rentals (e.g., Airbnb, internet-based bike sharing) all forms part of this (although garnering differential treatment from the state). Second, is to look at the practices as graded via our understanding of the urban, where study of street-vending falls under the investigation of informality (Sekhani et al., 2019; Tucker and Devlin, 2019), while internet-based rentals become one that of economics (Ferreri and Sanyal, 2018; Guttentag, 2015). This difference in enquiry exists because of the epistemological manoeuvre of investigations trying to understand informality, as evident in the form of marginalization. If, on the other hand, we intend to read the urban via informality, then it will lead to outlining of various informal practices and its treatment both by the state and in the academic research, highlighting southern theory's interest of locating the knowledge hegemony. Here the urban become a relational entity (Massey, 1993; Parnell and Robinson, 2012; Simone, 2010; Ward, 2010) and informality one of the many practices, resulting from and constituent of, the politics of relationships. This position highlights the operational utility of informality, towards both, understanding and reformulating, what it means to be urban. This shifts investigation of urban towards the knowledge politics – determining which informal practices are termed informal and which are not.

This knowledge politics can be situated in the contemporary urban debates of global circulation of capital and relational understanding of the urban. Brenner (2000), revisiting the urban question, took Sassen's global narrative and focused the economic concerns to space and society using Lefebvre (1991). He put the urban question in, what

he called, the “contemporary period of global restructuring” (Brenner, 2000: 362). For Brenner, cities are not just to be seen as nodes of global capital movement as conceptualized by Sassen, but also how this, becoming of nodes and peripheries, quintessentially changes the way cities and its occupants operate, thus, the need for critically refreshing both the urban question and consequently, critical urban theory. This conceptualization, led to questioning the very way we know the urban, resulting Brenner and Schmid (2015) to broaden the Sassen(esque) question of global cities and network, to Lefebvre’s planetary urbanization. The urban, for Brenner and Schmid, is a multi-scalar transformation, which may or may not result in agglomeration, thus there being no other way than to look at planetary urbanization – a process where the form (agglomeration/ city) is irrelevant. Alongside, Robinson (2002) also built her work on the critique of the global-city concept. She argued that global cities are just like a business district within a city and they should not be allowed to overshadow other (parts of) cities which are the habitats for majority of the urban dwellers. She further argued that every city is to be studied as an ordinary city (Amin and Graham, 1997) (beyond global city rankings) and the western capitalist model of a city cannot dominate and should not be the medium to understand or marginalize other cities (Robinson, 2006). This being a call for a renewed comparative urban studies which develops its own possibilities of looking at cities of the Global South (Robinson, 2016). Although conceptually different, these works need to be understood as the ongoing restructuring of what it means to be urban (Derickson, 2015), from Brenner and Schmid's (2015) moving of beyond city form to Robinson's (2006) enquiry of cities outside the global-city hierarchies.

Let us briefly read the ongoing restructuring of the urban debates from a southern theory perspective. Connell (2011) outlined how the theories emanating from the North have always had a universal tone, devoid of time and place. That is, they are applicable everywhere (in any context) and at any time (timeless). She argued that these universal claims emanate partly because things are seen from the centre (metropolis) (Connell, 2014). It is the concerns raised in the metropolis that becomes the object of study in the periphery, therefore enhancing these universal theories further. For this to happen, of course, certain issues need to be excluded that are not a concern in the metropolis. Further, Comaroff and Comaroff (2012), problematized the notion of the South itself. They conceptualized it as a relation arising from the hegemony of the North (pointed by Connell and Robinson as well). Discussing the case of Euro-American corporations’ indulgence in political affairs of African democracies, they argue:

“ ... “the south” cannot be defined, a *priori*, in substantive terms. The label bespeaks a *relation*, not a thing in or for itself. It is a historical artifact, a labile signifier in a grammar of signs whose semiotic content is determined, over time, by everyday material, political, and cultural processes, the dialectical products of a global world in motion.”(Comaroff and Comaroff, 2012: 47) [emphasis original].

Therefore, if we render South as a political category and not a geographical one, then it is a logical fallacy to develop a southern turn by epistemological probing . The alternate way would be for an ontological enquiry – on deriving questions from the South itself. Looking from the metropolis, trying to understand informality, the broader question that gets framed is – how the formal urbanization process and the formal city operate in the presence of informality, or a slightly complex notion of, how the formal urbanization process and the formal city negotiates, controls, or works with informality, resulting in epistemological innovations. These innovations lead to conceptualization of urban outside the North as an alternative, with a suffix to notify that the urban processes elsewhere are an anomaly to the ‘real’ urban (Benjamin, 2008; Karaman et al., 2020). One of the plausible ways out of this conundrum is to invert the above question. That the aim be not to understand informality by epistemological tweaking of the formal urban/urbanization, rather the aim be to understand the urban/urbanization using informality. Herein South being a “time-limited concept-metaphor” (Lawhon and Truelove, 2020: 14) for a call to make urban theory global, to an extent that the notion of south dissolves eventually.

The juxtaposition of literature arguing restructuring of urban conceptualization and southern theory is done here for renewing the ontological position of informality (with respect to the urban). When we are in a process of broadening the understanding of urban and arguing against the northern centeredness of theory, enquiring informality as a special case within urban is stifling. Reading the urban via informality presents two particular directions. First, it highlights the knowledge politics of marginalization (both within and beyond the city). For example, the rendering of certain informal practices as informal and certain as not, presents the scope for investigating the concentration of power and knowledge. It is not merely to uncover the manifestations that informal practices of the rich get state legitimacy while that of the poor does not, but articulation of an investigation of urban conceptualization that led to this. For example, to investigate the urban in which informality in the North (by the state) is rendered in positive light (desirable) as opposed to in the South (corrupt) (Jaffe and

Koster, 2019). Second, investigation of informal and formal practices by same bodies in different context, reveals, the situated urban conception of those particular bodies. For example, the residents of slums (the legal category) in Delhi, informally construct houses without municipal building permits (an informal practice) however goes to extreme lengths to pay electricity bills (formal practice) and keep meticulous records of the same (Auerbach, 2018). The urban as experienced and understood by the particular residents of the slum, in this manner could be theorized beyond the metropolitan notions of the urban. This differential understanding of urban becomes relatable to Massey's (1993) power-geometry conceptualization. Coupling space and time, she lucidly puts:

“Different social groups have distinct relationships to this anyway-differentiated mobility [originating from space-time compression]: some are more in charge of it than others; some initiate flows and movement, others don't; some are more on the receiving end of it than others; some are effectively imprisoned by it.”(Massey, 1993: 61)

In the attempt to conceptualize urban from a world of cities (Derickson, 2015; Lawhon et al., 2020; Lawhon and Le Roux, 2019), we need to also add the snippet that these cities means and operate differently to different residents. It is not just that the urban is varied, but these urban means conceptually different, resulting in different ways of operating, imagining, and interacting in/with it (Palat Narayanan, 2020c). Attempting the transportation of informality across the North-South divide Boudreau (2019: 597) argued that:

Harnessing the heuristic potential of informality crucially relies on taking informality 'out' of the global South and using it as a device to understand the global North and its 'high-capacity states'.

I would like to adapt the state-centric notion of Boudreau (2019) within the urban. If the urban is varied (beyond the conceptual clustering of North and South) and its conceptualization is currently under review, then, informality becomes an important concept of urban enquiry. It highlights the politics of urban knowledge production, wherein certain informal practices are studied as informal and certain not; and enables an enquiry into the bodies, places of practising informality, and the inherent urban experiences/conceptions that lead to this. Consequently, reformulating (beginning with updating) what it means to be urban using the first two forms of enquiry.

It should, be noted here that informality has also been a subject of enquiry in the northern cities (Chiodeli et al., 2020; Devlin, 2011; Esposito and Chiodeli, 2020; Fairbanks, 2011; Grashoff, 2019), although, comparatively less owing to what Jaffe and Koster (2019: 563) calls “the myth of Northern formality”. However, investigating informality across the North-South divide is not enough, if not coupled with the interrogation of the urban.

The current debates of ordinary city (Robinson, 2006), planetary urbanism (Brenner and Schmid, 2015), and southern theory (Connell, 2011), have all been for one a call for the restructuring of the urban. This section took these debates to discuss the larger point to place informality research as a means to investigate urban. It did this using three prospective agendas. First, the very definition of informality within an urban, puts the idea of urban in question, thus leading to read informality within the informal-urban dialectic. Second, informality studied in the context of knowledge hegemony uncovers the knowledge politics which defines the urban. Finally, informality as a practice, heuristically delivers the tool, to investigate the variegated notions of urban as situated from the practices of the dwellers. Although informality is a notion that is highly contested, placing it within the informal-urban dialectic presents the potential of using this concept as a means to restructure critical urban theory.

V Conclusion

This article juxtaposed southern theory perspective on informality discussions and set out an agenda that prioritizes ontological queries in informality research. It argued that, to counter the metropolitan bias, we need to have methodological and theoretical innovation in deriving concerns from the periphery, contrary to epistemological innovation which answers the concerns of the metropolis from the periphery.

Furthermore, it showed that the urban have been understood via formal practices and informality is studied as deviance to this constructed idea of urban. The aim here was not to develop a comprehensive understanding of the urban (Scott and Storper, 2015), but to use informality as a heuristic tool to highlight the hegemonic nature of knowledge production (Leitner and Sheppard, 2016; Robinson, 2003). Informality studies have long concentrated on state brutalities and citizen’s counter campaign, and in this process the research agenda was set to understand informality. The article aimed to rupture this continuity by pointing out the seemingly radical politics of studying informality has had a metropolitan bias and is rooted in hegemonic discourse.

Southern theory postulates the need for theorizing from the south and informality has been theorized from the south. In this case, the befitting question is – is informality (as a theorization) quintessentially a southern theory? I argue that it is not, as the conceptualization of informality has had a metropolitan bias. However, offsetting the bias, presents a potent field to develop a southern theory approach to the urban.

~~Furthermore, the article showed that the epistemological innovation in reading informality has fallen prey to answering the metropolitan concerns in the periphery.~~

The need for epistemological innovation arises from the research premise of understanding informality as deviance to the ideal-type urban. The notion of urban is taken as absolute and universal, which is based, on few western cities. As informality does not conform to this ideal-type, there arises the need for newer ways to understand it. One of the means to counter this is to reverse the research premise. If we try to understand the urban via informality, the established notions of urban (the ideal-type urban) diminish and as informality becomes the tool to understand the urban, the ontological prism gain prominence (Palat Narayanan and Véron, 2018). Theoretically, this was made possible by reading informality within the informal-urban dialectic, where the inquiry of informality has to investigate the urban itself.

During the initial conceptualization of informality as the informal sector, the main concern was the failure of the economic model to accommodate it. This economic model conceptualized an urban where economic transactions are registered or is theoretically visible to the state. The Informal sector was an anomaly to this model, as the economic transactions were not registered. This called for an epistemological tweaking, by trying to understand traits like education, poverty, migration status, etc. Such traits were identified to look for the links between people who practised informality and their deviance from the western norms of an ideal city dweller. As the contrast was the ideal city dweller, much of the informal sector was rendered as rural or not yet urban, a much-critiqued strain of the Chicago School (AlSayyad, 2004; Bayat, 2000). As the world started to globalize, the nature of interest in informality also shifted. The economic champions of globalization process reinforced themselves as North and others became South, which makes geographic sense reading it through Massey's (1993) conception of power-geometry, when one is looking at South America from North America, or Africa from Europe. These economic disparities started to render cities in the South as an anomaly to the few global cities of the North. Urban informality took much of the blame for this anomaly (Jaffe and Koster, 2019), as it represented slums and substandard

housing (Amin, 2013; Ghertner, 2013). The southern theory perspective argued otherwise and looked for theoretical projects within the South. However, within the southern theory paradigm, research on informality continued to make it comprehensible, when seen from the metropolis. The main theme being to uncover and highlight the nuanced multitude of processes through which informality evolves, resists, and operate. For such an exercise, the main requirement is epistemological innovation. Reading the informality research through this perspective, it showed a gap in accommodating concerns from the South for understanding informality, i.e., in not trying to explain informality in contrast to the western city, but ontologically investigating the urban via informality.

Further, urban informality became a trope with which the urbanization process in the South was understood. The pressing need to understand the urban growth in the South, a snippet with which this article started, pushed the research on informality further in this direction. Deriving from the broad outline of informality in this article, we can identify the keystone for this position is the ambition to understand informality via the 'ideal' urban, as deviance to it. It is in this context that the article modestly proposes to reverse the archetype, remove the keystone and let the arch fall. Understanding the urban via informality opens up a theoretical avenue, where the quintessential ideal-type urban, is no longer needed to study cities, either in the South or elsewhere. I do not singularly argue this position as a mode to develop urban theory and informality as a heuristic device, but them as a mode to be able to question our position as researchers and highlight the metropolitan bias which is not prominently rendered otherwise.

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